

**PNRR - MISSIONE 4, COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.1 - BANDO
PRIN 2022 PNRR - DECRETO DIRETTORIALE N. 1409 DEL 14-09-2022**

ID project number: P2022PY3AC

CUP: J53D23013850001

Project Acronym: HYDRA

Project title: Hydrochar application for Improving plants performance under stress: a promising pathway to support the transition to a circular economy

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

1. Data description

The project has produced three main data blocks:

- Data Block 1: dataset produced during the project and ready for public release.
- Data Block 2: dataset produced during the project.
- Data Block 3: dataset produced during the project.

The data consist of numerical data obtained by measuring several parameters and will be stored in open and widely used formats (e.g. CSV, excel, txt).

2. Data availability and access

- Data Block 1 is publicly available through Zenodo, with a persistent identifier (DOI).
- Data Blocks 2 and 3 are deposited in Zenodo but are subject to a temporary embargo. During the embargo period, access to the data is restricted.
- After the embargo period, all datasets will be made openly available in compliance with FAIR principles and PRIN PNRR Open Science requirements.

3. Embargo period

The embargo for Data Blocks 2 and 3 lasts until the publication of the main scientific results. The embargo is required to allow data validation, analysis, and scientific dissemination.

4. Documentation and metadata

All datasets will be accompanied by standard metadata provided by Zenodo, including description, authorship, date of creation, methodology, and usage license, to ensure data reusability.

5. Data storage and preservation

All datasets will be stored and preserved in Zenodo, an open and trusted repository supported by OpenAIRE, which guarantees long-term preservation and assignment of persistent identifiers (DOIs).

6. Contributors to Data Collection

Patrizia Trifilò (university of Messina), Giovanna Battipaglia (University of Campania L. Vanvitelli), Antonio Lupini (University Mediterranea of Reggio Calabria), Giuseppa Genovese (University of Messina), Claudia Espro (University of Messina), Alessandro crisafulli (University of Messian) Stefano Mileto (University of Messina), Damiano Spagnuolo (University of Messina), Francesco Niccoli (University of Campania L. Vanvitelli).

7. Ethical and legal aspects

The project does not involve personal or sensitive data.